

A Reproduction of BARO: Robust Root Cause Analysis for Microservices via Multivariate Bayesian Online Change Point Detection

Luan Pham
RMIT University
Australia
luan.pham@rmit.edu.au

Huong Ha
RMIT University
Australia
huong.ha@rmit.edu.au

Hongyu Zhang
Chongqing University
China
hyzhang@cqu.edu.cn

Badge claimed: [Replicated](#) or [Reproduced](#).

Reviewer skills: Familiarity with microservice architectures and empirical software engineering evaluation methodologies. No specific software execution or environment is required.

1 WHO

The original paper *BARO: Robust Root Cause Analysis for Microservices via Multivariate Bayesian Online Change Point Detection* [11] was authored by Luan Pham, Huong Ha, and Hongyu Zhang. Corresponding author: Luan Pham (luan.pham@rmit.edu.au). DOIs:

- Original paper: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3660805>
- Software: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094092> [10]
- Datasets: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11046533> [9]

Since publication, **16 independent research teams** have reproduced BARO’s main results using the provided artifacts (Table 1). The reproducing studies are cited in the references [1, 3–8, 12–20].

2 WHAT

BARO is an end-to-end framework integrating anomaly detection with root cause analysis (RCA) for microservices. It combines Multivariate Bayesian Online Change Point Detection (MBOCPD) for detecting anomalous periods with RobustScorer, a nonparametric statistical hypothesis testing technique, for ranking root cause candidates. The main results are: (1) state-of-the-art RCA accuracy on three benchmark microservice systems, (2) robustness to imprecise anomaly detection timing, and (3) sub-second RCA execution.

3 WHY

Root cause analysis is critical for maintaining the reliability of microservice architectures, which are increasingly adopted in cloud-native systems. BARO received the **ACM SIGSOFT Distinguished Artifact Award** at FSE 2024, recognizing the quality and reusability of its artifacts. Its adoption by 16 independent teams within two years, spanning academia and industry labs (Cisco [14], NTT [4, 5], NEC Labs [19, 20]) across 10 countries, underscores BARO’s impact. A recent comprehensive survey [2] highlights BARO as an exemplar of open, reproducible research in the field.

4 HOW

In the original study, BARO was evaluated on three benchmark microservice systems deployed on a 5-node Kubernetes cluster: Online Boutique (OB, 12 services), Sock Shop (SS, 11 services), and Train Ticket (TT, 64 services). Four fault types were injected (CPU overload, memory leak, network delay, packet loss) with ~100 cases per system (~300 total). BARO achieved coarse-grained Avg@5

of 0.86 (OB), 0.95 (SS), and 0.81 (TT); fine-grained Avg@5 of 0.61 (OB), 0.81 (SS), and 0.67 (TT). All artifacts were released on GitHub (phanquilluan/baro), PyPI (fse-baro), and Zenodo with DOIs.

5 WHERE

Table 1 summarizes the 16 independent studies that reproduced BARO’s results using the provided artifacts. These span institutions across North America, Europe, and Asia-Pacific. All 16 studies used BARO’s publicly released code; 7 also used BARO’s original benchmark datasets. The reproductions confirm BARO’s main findings:

RCA Accuracy. Fukuda et al. [4] obtained fine-grained Avg@5 of 0.81/0.61/0.66 on SS/OB/TT, closely matching BARO’s reported 0.81/0.61/0.67. Altenbernd et al. [1] confirmed Avg@5 up to 0.94 on Sock Shop and stated that BARO “outperforms current baselines.” Wang et al. [14] reproduced Avg@5 of 0.74–0.80 on the RCAEval benchmark. Liatsas et al. [7] reproduced Avg@5 = 0.88 on Online Boutique using BARO’s released dataset. On new datasets, Xie et al. [16] (ICSE ’26) noted that “BARO perform[s] relatively better due to [its] more accurate modeling of fault propagation,” and Liu et al. [8] obtained Avg@5 = 0.744 on an AIOps benchmark.

Robustness. Altenbernd et al. [1] confirmed that “only BARO provides robustness with respect to the anomaly detector,” directly validating BARO’s key claim of insensitivity to anomaly detection.

Efficiency. Fang et al. [3] confirmed BARO as the fastest method in their benchmark (0.99s total). Liatsas et al. [7] and Altenbernd et al. [1] confirmed sub-second RCA execution (0.01–0.21s across all datasets).

Generalizability. Multiple teams extended BARO’s evaluation to new domains beyond the original study: LLM inference systems [12], 5G core networks [5], multi-modal data sources [19, 20], DeathStarBench [15], and large-scale industrial benchmarks [8, 16, 17], further demonstrating the utility of BARO’s artifacts.

6 DISCUSSION

Several factors facilitated reproduction: (1) multiple distribution channels (GitHub, PyPI, Zenodo) lowered adoption barriers; (2) comprehensive documentation, tutorials, and Jupyter notebooks enabled quick setup; (3) continuous integration (CircleCI, GitHub Actions) ensured code quality and prevented code rot; and (4) the RCAEval benchmark framework provided a standardized evaluation environment. Challenges identified by reproducing teams include scalability beyond 100 microservices [15] and reduced performance on non-microservice domains [5, 20]. These findings help delineate BARO’s scope without contradicting its original claims.

Table 1: Summary of 16 independent studies reproducing BARO’s results using author-provided artifacts. “Code” and “Data” indicate use of BARO’s released code and datasets, respectively. OB = Online Boutique, SS = Sock Shop, TT = Train Ticket.

#	Study	Venue/Year	Code	Data	Key BARO Metrics Reproduced
1	Xie et al. [16]	ICSE '26	✓		Top-1: 0.048–0.615, MRR: 0.212–0.776 (4 datasets)
2	Zheng et al. [20]	arXiv '24	✓		PR@1: 0.00–0.75, MRR: 0.085–0.775 (4 datasets)
3	Ikram et al. [6]	UAI '25	✓	✓	Top-1: 1.00 (SS), ranks 6–9 (production data)
4	Altenbernd et al. [1]	FSE-C '25	✓	✓	Avg@5: 0.83–0.94 (SS, OB, TT, 6 variants)
5	Fukuda et al. [4]	ICWS '25	✓	✓	Avg@5: 0.81 (SS), 0.61 (OB), 0.66 (TT)
6	Liu et al. [8]	IWQoS '25	✓		HR@1: 0.621, HR@5: 0.828, Avg@5: 0.744
7	Wang et al. [14]	IEEE Access '25	✓	✓	Avg@5: 0.74 (OB), 0.77 (SS), 0.80 (TT)
8	Liatsas et al. [7]	NFV-SDN '25	✓	✓	AC@1: 0.72, Avg@5: 0.88, F1: 0.89 (OB)
9	Fukuda et al. [5]	GLOBECOM '25	✓		MRR: 0.115, Avg@5: 0.067 (5G core network)
10	Zheng et al. [19]	BigData '25	✓		PR@1: 0.50, MRR: 0.537 (Product Review)
11	Zhang et al. [17]	2025	✓	✓	AC@1: 0.144–0.263, Avg@5: 0.476–0.776
12	Zhang et al. [18]	ISSRE '25	✓		Precision: 0.481–0.547, F1: 0.369–0.480
13	Tian et al. [13]	2025	✓	✓	AC@1: 0.144, Avg@5: 0.742 (RE2-OB)
14	Winchester et al. [15]	2025	✓		Avg@5: 0.00–0.88, F1: 0.11–0.89 (DSB)
15	Fang et al. [3]	FSE '26	✓		Top@1: 0.36, Avg@5: 0.48, Time: 0.99s
16	Scheinert et al. [12]	2026	✓		AC@1: 0.13–0.77, Avg@5: 0.41–0.91 (LLM)

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